

**Report on the Cultural Heritage Survey for the TAPI
Project, Afghanistan
Pilot Phase
EAMENA-ICONEM
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1. Executive Summary

Afghanistan's rich cultural heritage, spanning from prehistoric times to the modern state, has been significantly impacted by decades of conflict and instability, as well as development and natural factors. The TAPI (Turkmenistan-Afghanistan-Pakistan-India) gas pipeline project, spanning over 1,600 kilometres and supported by the Asian Development Bank, will pose additional risks to cultural heritage sites in Afghanistan due to its extensive construction and operational phases once construction begins.

To address these challenges, the Endangered Archaeology in the Middle East and North Africa (EAMENA) project at the University of Oxford, in collaboration with ICONEM, conducted a pilot study to document heritage sites along over 338 km of the pipeline corridor in Kandahar and Helmand provinces using remote sensing techniques. This initiative aims to provide an open-access dataset and establish a baseline for further remote monitoring of heritage resources in Afghanistan, adhering to the FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability) principles.

The pilot phase identified 433 heritage sites, including archaeological sites, historical settlements and structures, cemeteries, and traditional irrigation systems, in the surveyed section of the TAPI. These sites are located at varying distances from the pipeline. Among them, 75 sites are within a 500-meter buffer zone of the pipeline, indicating a first-degree threat from pipeline construction and associated activities. Among these sites, 37 *qanat* or *kariz* systems (subterranean irrigation channels) are at direct risk of being cut off, representing about 23% of the recorded qanats in the project area. In addition to their heritage values, these ancient but still functioning underground water supply systems are crucial for agriculture and the livelihoods of rural communities, necessitating special attention to potential damage during pipeline construction.

The dataset, maintained in the EAMENA database on the Arches platform, is accessible to Afghan heritage authorities, the TAPI project, the Environmental and Social Impact Assessment (ESIA) team, and interested researchers and heritage professionals. The data collection and analysis followed EAMENA's methodology for documenting endangered archaeological resources, utilising free remote sensing data from Google Earth and other sources.

This report aims to assist in heritage preservation, mitigate development risks, and raise awareness about Afghanistan's cultural heritage and its threats. The initiative also seeks to establish a methodology for Afghan researchers and heritage professionals interested in documenting, monitoring, and managing cultural heritage resources using open-access satellite imagery and open-source software.

Ultimately, the project underscores the need for continued efforts to protect and preserve Afghanistan's invaluable cultural heritage in the face of ongoing development and natural challenges.

2. Overview

Afghanistan's history spans from prehistoric times to the establishment of the modern state. Early inhabitants settled in the region at least as far back as 50,000 years ago, although there is some evidence for earlier occupation from c 100,000 years ago and evidence from Iran suggests Afghanistan may have been on early hominin dispersal routes. There is evidence of Neolithic farming communities around 9,000 years ago with contacts to both the Neolithic of Tajikistan and Eastern Iran. These regional cultural networks grew through the Chalcolithic and Bronze Ages as seen in painted pottery and metallurgy. The region was part of various empires, by the end of the Iron Age, including the Achaemenid Empire in the 6th century BCE and Alexander the Great's empire in the 4th century BCE. The area later became a cultural and commercial hub under the Kushan Empire around the 1st to 3rd centuries CE. In the Islamic era, it was ruled by the Samanids, Ghaznavids, and Ghurids. The 13th century saw the Mongol invasion. In the 18th century, Ahmad Shah Durrani founded the modern state of Afghanistan, uniting various tribes and regions into a single kingdom, which laid the foundation for contemporary Afghanistan.

In recent decades, Afghanistan's cultural heritage, including archaeological sites, historical centres and monuments, museums, landscapes, and even intangible heritage, has suffered serious and sometimes irreparable damage due to various factors. These include war and instability, deliberate destruction, looting and illicit trafficking, unsustainable development, mining, agriculture, natural disasters, and a lack of investment in management, protection, and monitoring. From 2003, following the establishment of the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan, to 2021, when the Taliban regained power, there was a significant presence of international institutions and projects focused on archaeology and cultural heritage. However, after the fall of Ashraf Ghani's government in 2021, much of this international cooperation ceased, and many Afghan researchers and cultural heritage experts left the country. The poor economic situation and lack of investment in the cultural heritage sector raise concerns about further damage to Afghanistan's cultural heritage.

In this context, efforts to monitor and raise awareness about the threats facing Afghanistan's invaluable heritage must continue. One relatively low-cost and quick method to monitor endangered archaeological sites and cultural heritage is the use of remote sensing techniques and satellite imagery.

Afghanistan's geological and geographical position has endowed the nation with substantial mineral resources and situated it in a strategically significant geopolitical location, serving as a vital nexus among Asian countries. While these resources and geopolitical advantages present considerable economic opportunities, their exploitation and extraction pose significant challenges to the preservation of Afghanistan's cultural and natural heritage.

Afghanistan's geology is characterised by a dynamic and tumultuous natural environment. Afghanistan is located at the boundary between the Indian and Eurasian tectonic plates and contains numerous fault lines. The resulting constant geological activity creates steep mountains and deeply incised valleys while earthquakes are frequent. There are fertile plains, rivers, and large lakes, although these resources are often affected by climate change which is increasing the frequency of flooding and dust storms, leading to desertification and soil erosion. Afghanistan's diverse geology includes vast deposits of exotic rocks, fault breccias, and other geological features, which contribute to its rugged terrain but provide rich mineral resources, although these are challenging to exploit due to the harsh environment. The history of the region reveals a constant struggle for survival, with the inhabitants adapting to and shaping their environment through irrigation and agriculture (Shroder 2014:13-14).

Afghanistan's mineral resources, most famously its lapis lazuli, have been exploited since prehistory. Modern exploration continues to discover major mineral resources. In 2010, an American survey identified significant deposits of iron, copper, cobalt, gold, and essential industrial metals such as lithium (Risen 2010). These resources, estimated to be worth between \$1 and \$3 trillion, have generated both optimism and apprehension (Sheraz 2014).

The TAPI Gas Pipeline Project (Phase 1), supported by The Asian Development Bank (ADB), aims to construct a pipeline extending approximately 1,600 kilometres from Turkmenistan through Afghanistan and Pakistan to India. Approximately 780 kilometres of the pipeline route pass through Afghanistan. The pipeline will transport 33 billion cubic meters of natural gas annually, with allocations of 5% to Afghanistan, and 47.5% each to Pakistan and India over a 30-year operational period. The project is split into two phases: Phase 1 involves the construction of the pipeline in Afghanistan and Pakistan, while Phase 2 includes installing six compressor stations to increase capacity (Asian Development Bank 2021). The TAPI gas pipeline project has the potential to significantly impact the region and shift the geopolitical landscape for countries benefiting from Central Asia's gas and oil reserves. Successfully completing the TAPI pipeline could enhance energy transfer, improve Pakistan-India relations, and foster regional cooperation and economic interdependence (Rajpoot & Naeem 2020: 21). The pipeline may enhance regional cooperation, diversify Turkmenistan's gas export markets, and support the economic development strategies of the involved countries.

Environmental and social aspects are crucial considerations, with the project classified as Category A for both environmental impact and involuntary resettlement. This classification is due to significant land use, potential livelihood impacts, and the transboundary nature of the pipeline. While indigenous peoples are not significantly impacted, the project affects various ethnic groups in Afghanistan and Pakistan (Asian Development Bank 2021).

A Joint Venture between Specialized Technologies for Petroleum Engineering (NAFTEC) and MAB Environmental Consultancy & Studies LLC (MAB) conducted an Environmental and Social Impact Assessment (ESIA) for the project. This assessment was approved by the Afghanistan National Environmental Protection Agency (NEPA) in August 2019. The initial ESIA identified around 100 households that would face physical displacement due to the project. To mitigate this impact, the pipeline was re-routed to avoid physical displacement and reduce economic displacement. The re-routing included relocating the initial 500-meter wide corridor, particularly in the Registan desert, to prevent affecting these households.

Although the TAPI project is aware of the cultural heritage protection requirements and has incorporated this aspect into its ESIA assessment, there remains a need for greater attention to the number and diversity of cultural heritage that could be impacted by TAPI. It is necessary to accurately identify cultural heritage resources within the project areas and then assess the potential impacts on them. Given the current challenges and significant limitations in conducting fieldwork in Afghanistan, remote sensing methods are the most highly useful and effective for examining and updating impact assessment reports.

For this purpose, the Endangered Archaeology in the Middle East and North Africa (EAMENA) project at the University of Oxford and ICONEM have collaborated on a pilot project to study a section of the TAPI pipeline in Kandahar and Helmand provinces, Afghanistan, from an archaeological perspective.

EAMENA

The Endangered Archaeology in the Middle East and North Africa (EAMENA) project has been funded by the Arcadia Fund since 2015 and the Cultural Protection Fund (CPF) of the British Council since 2016 in response to threats to archaeological sites in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA). It covers countries from Afghanistan to Mauritania. The project uses remote sensing to document at-risk archaeological sites and historical landscapes. EAMENA is based at the School of Archaeology of the University of Oxford in partnership with the Universities of Leicester and Durham, and with many governmental, educational and NGO partners throughout the region. As of July 2024, the EAMENA database contains over 383,000 records in the MENA region.

ICONEM

ICONEM is a French start-up specialised in architectural assessment and 3D digitisation of endangered cultural heritage sites. Its team has worked extensively in over 40 countries and over 350 sites, including areas such as Lebanon, Afghanistan, Syria, Yemen, and Iraq. ICONEM's approach combines large-scale data acquisition of entire urban areas with high resolution photogrammetry of finer-grained details, relying on the photorealistic quality of 3D to create

digital replicas of cultural heritage sites. Over the course of these projects, ICONEM has developed an ability to rapidly handle complex logistical situations, while providing high-resolution analysis of architectural structures.

3. Objectives of this report

The objective of this report is to demonstrate a powerful methodology for conducting archaeological and heritage assessments in advance of development. It achieves this by presenting the dataset gathered in the pilot phase of a prospection survey for archaeological and cultural heritage resources around a section of the TAPI pipeline. This dataset can then be used to help mitigate the risks that the development project poses to these sites. The report is intended to be shared with heritage and antiquities authorities in Afghanistan, the TAPI project, and the ESIA assessment team. It provides the results of a detailed archaeological remote survey to review and update the cultural heritage potentially impacted by the project. The report also aims to establish a baseline methodology for monitoring at-risk archaeological resources in Afghanistan by demonstrating the capabilities of freely available satellite imagery. Utilising a state-of-the-art digital database and data management system, this endeavour adheres to the FAIR Principles, providing an open-access, Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable dataset. This dataset is intended not only for heritage authorities and the TAPI project but also for communities and researchers interested in Afghanistan's cultural heritage.

4. Methodology

Data collection and recording followed the EAMENA project's methodology for documenting endangered archaeological resources (Rouhani & Huet 2024), primarily utilising free remote sensing data on Google Earth from providers such as CNES/Airbus, Landsat/Copernicus, and others. Employing the EAMENA framework, the entire project area is divided into grid squares of 0.25 degrees in longitude and latitude, roughly equating to 25×27 kilometers depending on the location. This grid system facilitates systematic scanning and visual inspection of satellite images for each square within the study area.

In selecting a pilot study area, it was decided to focus on a segment of the project with a proportionately diverse range of heritage sites. A preliminary satellite survey, along with cross-referencing the DAFA (French Archaeological Delegation in Afghanistan) database, indicated that the segment in the Helmand and Kandahar regions, starting from the border with Pakistan, would present a varied range of heritage sites around the pipeline for further condition assessment. Other surveys, such as the Afghan Heritage Mapping Partnership (AHMP) from the University of Chicago, have also been consulted for this purpose (Franklin & Hammer 2018).

The exact footprint of the construction works for the pipeline and the associated buffer zone was obtained using documents published by the Asian Development Bank, which include pages extracted from a GIS project in an appendix¹. The area surveyed in this pilot study covers approximately 338 km of the pipeline, spanning over 16 EAMENA grid squares.

The map shows the EAMENA grid squares assessed by EAMENA and ICONEM.

Heritage places, including archaeological sites, historical settlements and structures, and traditional irrigation systems, were identified and recorded through visual examination of Google Earth satellite images. Their overall preservation condition and disturbance factors were assessed using Google Earth's time slider, which allows for comparison of images from different time periods. The imagery covered a time span from 2002 to 2023. For each heritage site, at least three high-quality satellite images from different time periods (the oldest, middle, and most recent) were examined, and in some cases, more than three periods were analysed.

¹ <https://www.adb.org/projects/52167-001/main>

All information was logged into the EAMENA database (<https://database.eamena.org/>), which uses various resource models to document heritage sites. The EAMENA database (version 4) is an online geospatial database built on Arches, an open-source software platform created by the Getty Conservation Institute and the World Monuments Fund. This database employs controlled vocabulary to standardise entries (see: <https://eamena.org/advanced-use#rm-hp-fields>).

5. Results

Within the study area, 433 heritage sites were identified and recorded at varying distances from the pipeline. To enhance data accessibility, all these sites were assigned "TAPI" as an alternative reference in the database. Given that the data collection relied primarily on remote sensing, pinpointing the cultural periods of the sites was often difficult. However, in some instances, cultural periods were determined through architectural analysis, structural comparisons between sites, and by consulting specific surveys and published reports mentioned in the methodology section. Similarly, there can be some uncertainty over the interpretation of what the identified sites represent, leading us to refer to Site Feature Interpretation, rather than site type.

Assessed archaeological sites along the TAPI pipeline. Note sites are only shown on the pipeline segment studied.

The identified heritage sites encompass a diverse range, including mounds or archaeological tells, qanats (underground irrigation channels, *qanats* or *kareez/kariz/karez-* and *foggara* in North Africa), buildings and enclosures, caravanserais (roadside inns), cemeteries and burials, as well as fortresses and castles. Approximately 156 *qanats* or *kareez/kariz* were identified within the study area, constituting 40% of the heritage sites along this section of the pipeline. Qanats are ancient and traditional underground irrigation channels used to transport water from an aquifer or water well to the surface for irrigation and drinking and can extend for several kilometres. Qanats consist of a gently sloping tunnel that channels water by gravity across long distances that avoid significant evaporation losses by being underground, making them particularly effective in arid regions. They typically feature vertical shafts, visible on satellite imagery, at intervals to access and maintain the tunnel. This ingenious system has been essential for agriculture and settlement in desert areas across the Middle East, North Africa, and beyond. This method of water supply, traditionally thought to have been introduced to Afghanistan during the Achaemenid period, has served as a crucial and dependable source of water for numerous rural villages, particularly in the southern regions of the country (Stinson et al. 2016; Stevenson et al. 2021; Goes et al. 2017).

The next most frequent classification of interpreted heritage (Site Feature Interpretation in the database glossary) are tells, which comprise approximately 30% of the sites in this area.

The site feature interpretations are presented in the diagram below.

An important aspect of our methodology is to make an assessment of the current condition of recorded sites. After a careful condition assessment using available satellite imagery, 40% of the sites were identified as being in poor overall condition. According to the EAMENA methodology, poor condition indicates "a site or element that shows moderate signs of active

deterioration and/or signs of moderate structural instability, and/or moderate areas of disruption and/or damage to the majority of the original features of interest. Some significant features are missing, but some features of interest remain." Over 17% of heritage sites are in very bad condition, and 13% have been destroyed. Approximately 24% are in fair condition, 0.5% are in good condition, and the condition of just over 3.5% of the sites is unknown without ground inspection.

Overall Condition of sites

A caravanserai (EAMENA Database ID: EAMENA-0253338) and an adjacent ruined structure near the pipeline (red line). Image: Google Earth 2023.

A qanat system (EAMENA ID: EAMENA-0253343) in the Kandahar region visible as a continuous linear pattern of circular features, the tops of shafts leading to the underground channel, which will be intersected by the pipeline (red line).

The most common existing disturbance cause categories identified among heritage places are natural (40%) and agricultural/pastoral (29%), followed by infrastructure/transport (24.7%) and

building/development (22%) (shown on the Figure above). Other categories include unknown (14%), funerary/memorial (6.5%), looting and illegal activities (4.9%), and management issues (4%). It should be noted that multiple disturbance factors can simultaneously affect a heritage site.

The images above, show two heritage places (marked with red dots), recorded in the database with EAMENA IDs EAMENA-0252431 and EAMENA-0252432, which are probably the remain of buildings and structures. These sites are in very poor condition, affected by natural erosion (water and/or wind action), agricultural activities (such as irrigation channels and ploughing), and infrastructure/transport developments (roads and tracks). The Google Earth image on the left shows the sites in 2009 and the image on the right the same sites in 2022.

This image shows the Khak Chupan caravanserai (EAMENA-0252461) in Kandahar province, marked with a red dot. The distance between this historic building and the pipeline (represented by the red line on the upper right of the image) is only about 330 meters, putting it at potential risk.

The caravanserai is already in very poor condition, impacted by natural factors and agricultural activities. The Google Earth images show the building in (on the left) 2013 and (on the right) 2022.

This image shows an archaeological tell or mound in the Shir'ali Kariz area of Kandahar province (EAMENA-0252441), located approximately 300 meters from the pipeline (the red line at the bottom left of the image). The site is already in poor condition, affected by infrastructure/transport (road/track), agricultural activities, natural factors, and erosion. The Google Earth image shows the site in 2022.

6. Heritage Places at Risk from TAPI

Our analysis shows that there are 75 sites within the 500-meter buffer zone on each side of the projected pipeline, indicating that they are at high risk from the TAPI construction and associated works.

Among the heritage sites located within the 500m buffer zone, 37 qanats are at direct risk of being cut off by the pipeline. This represents about 23% of the recorded qanats within this part of the

project area. Qanats hold heritage value not only as traditional water management systems but also because many of them are still active and play a crucial role in the lives of rural people and agriculture. Special attention should therefore be paid to the potential damage to the qanats during the construction of this pipeline, considering not only their heritage values but also their environmental, ecological, economic, and social significance.

We identified a further 46 sites within a 500-1000-meter buffer zone, indicating a second-degree threat. Additionally, 34 more sites are located within a 1000-1500-meter buffer zone, indicating a third-degree threat. The remaining sites identified are outwith this distance, and we anticipate that there should not be any significant risk to them from the construction project.

The most threatened sites by the construction of the TAPI Pipeline

The above map shows some examples of the qanat systems within the first buffer zone (500m) from the pipeline in EAMENA grids E65N31-31 and E64N31-42. The grids' locations are highlighted in the inset map at the top right.

7. Data Accessibility

Decades of conflict and instability have severely undermined cultural heritage management in Afghanistan. Furthermore, the absence of open-access cultural heritage databases documenting disturbances and threats presents a significant challenge to the management, preservation, and research of Afghanistan's cultural heritage. This initiative, therefore, seeks to provide an open-

access dataset and establish a baseline for the further remote monitoring of heritage resources in the country.

All data are recorded in the EAMENA database (<https://database.eamena.org/>), which is maintained on Arches v7 software developed by the Getty Conservation Institute for cultural heritage management. Access to the data is based on the principle of “As open as possible, as closed as necessary,” and we strive to follow the FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability) principles. There are three levels of access to the database: Public access, Research access, and Contributor access². While there are some limitations for public access (largely at the request of national heritage agencies to reduce the potential of the database being used to assist looting), those registered with research access can access the full report on each of the recorded heritage places, including the precise location and condition assessment. The data will be freely accessible to Afghan heritage and antiquities authorities, the TAPI project team, and the ESIA assessment team for purposes of research and heritage preservation planning. The steps for registration on the EAMENA database are explained on the EAMENA website³, where a simple form to request research access is also available⁴. There is no cost for any level of access.

All heritage places around the TAPI pipeline have been labelled "TAPI" as their alternative reference, making searching them seamless in the database by simply typing "TAPI" as the Heritage Place-Resource name in the database search box. More advanced searches can also be conducted in the database.

Heritage places are additionally recorded under the “Heritage Dataset around TAPI Pipeline, Afghanistan by EAMENA/ICONEM- Pilot Phase” EAMENA Zenodo community.

The dataset can be cited as follows:

EAMENA database (2024) ‘Heritage Dataset around TAPI Pipeline, Afghanistan by EAMENA/ICONEM- Pilot Phase’. Zenodo.

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Additionally, registered researchers will have access to the data for studies concerning Afghanistan's cultural heritage and potential threats to these sites.

² EAMENA Open Access Policy: <https://eamena.org/open-access-policy>

³ <https://eamena.org/database>

⁴ <https://eamena.org/database-registration-form>

8. Next Steps

This pilot phase of documenting heritage sites along the TAPI pipeline was conducted collaboratively by EAMENA and ICONEM funded by the Arcadia grant held by EAMENA. Both EAMENA and ICONEM aim to complete the documentation of additional heritage sites along the TAPI pipeline, contingent upon further funding. Beyond aiding in heritage preservation and mitigating development risks to cultural heritage resources, this initiative seeks to enhance awareness of Afghanistan's rich cultural heritage, the threats it faces, and the needs arising from development projects and other factors such as natural and climatic threats. We also aim to establish a methodology for Afghan researchers and heritage professionals interested in documenting, monitoring, and managing cultural heritage resources using open-access satellite data and open-source software.

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